

Supplementary materials to

Environmental variability, reliability of information and the timing of migration

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Supplementary Material S1: Dynamic programming equations

Terminal reward

Set $V(i, k, N) = 0$ for all $i = -Q, -(Q - 1), \dots, 0, 1, 2, \dots, Q$ and all $k = 0, 1, \dots, K - 1$.

Set $V(i, K, n) = R(i\Delta, n\Delta)$ for all $i = -Q, -(Q - 1), \dots, 0, 1, 2, \dots, Q$ and all $n = 0, 1, \dots, N$.

Backwards step

Let $0 \leq n \leq N - 1$. Suppose that $V(i, k, n + 1)$ is given for all $i = -Q, -(Q - 1), \dots, 0, 1, 2, \dots, Q$ and all $k = 0, 1, \dots, K$.

for each $i = -Q, -(Q - 1), \dots, 0, 1, 2, \dots, Q$ and each $k = 0, 1, \dots, K - 1$:

$$\text{Let } H_{\text{stay}} = [1 - M((n + i)\Delta, k)\Delta]V(i, k, n + 1)$$

$$\text{Let } H_{\text{leave}} = \sum_{j=-Q}^Q a_{i,j}(k + 1)V(j, k + 1, n + 1) \quad (***)$$

$$\text{Set } V(i, k, n) = \max\{H_{\text{stay}}, H_{\text{leave}}\}$$

Set $\text{Action}(i, k, n) = 1$ if $H_{\text{stay}} \geq H_{\text{leave}}$, else set $\text{Action}(i, k, n) = 0$.

[Note migration takes one time-unit in the above, but delta is small.]

The leaving strategy

If the optimal strategy is of the obvious simple form, then

$$L(i\Delta, k) = \Delta \sum_{n=0}^N \text{action}(i, k, n).$$

Numerical implementation

We draw a distinction between grid time and real time. Specifically, the time-grid step is Δ , which will typically be small. The time grid takes integer values of $n = 0, 1, 2, \dots, N$. These values correspond to

calendar times $t = 0, \Delta, 2\Delta, \dots, N\Delta$. The advancement of spring relative to the mean is assumed to lie on a grid $i = -Q, -(Q-1), \dots, 0, 1, 2, \dots, Q$. Grid time q corresponds to real time $q\Delta$.

The transition matrices

Define the function *fnorm* by

$$fnorm(x, m, v) = \exp\{-(x - m)^2 / 2v\}.$$

For each k in the range $k = 1, 2, \dots, K$,

$$\text{Set } v = \sigma^2(k)(1 - (\rho(k))^2).$$

For each i in the range $i = -Q, -(Q - 1), \dots, 0, 1, 2, \dots, Q$ set $m = i\Delta\rho(k)\sigma(k) / \sigma(k - 1)$

{ For each j are in the range $j = -Q, -(Q - 1), \dots, 0, 1, 2, \dots, Q$ set $x = j\Delta$.

$$\text{Set } \tilde{a}_{i,j}(k) = fnorm(x, m, v) . \}$$

$$\text{Set } sum = \sum_{j=-Q}^Q \tilde{a}_{i,j}(k) .$$

For each j in the range $j = -Q, -(Q - 1), \dots, 0, 1, 2, \dots, Q$ set $a_{i,j}(k) = \tilde{a}_{i,j}(k) / sum$.

[We can interpret these variables as follows:

$$a_{i,j}(k) = P(Y(k) = \Delta j \vee Y(k - 1) = \Delta i),$$

and $A(k) \equiv (a_{i,j}(k))$ is the transition matrix related the (grid values of) advancement of spring at location $k-1$ to that at k .]

Figure S1 – Relation between landscape ρ and $\rho(k)$

Fig. S1. As the landscape ρ is the product of all $\rho(k)$'s, changing the number of sites, K , while keeping the landscape ρ constant, changes the correlation between successive sites, $\rho(k)$. If the landscape ρ is either very high or very low, the correlations between successive sites, $\rho(k)$, hardly differ from landscape ρ , while the greatest differences appear for low to intermediate ρ and these differences increase further with more sites (darker lines).

Figure S2 – Reproductive values for varying number of sites and sigma

Fig. S2. Reproductive values over a gradient of overall predictability (landscape ρ) and environmental variability (upper panel) and varying number of sites (lower panel), respectively.

Adding intermediate sites does not yield any fitness-benefit in almost constant environment (d) while it clearly increases reproductive values when environments become more variable (e-f).